

Digital Ancient Near Eastern
Studies Conference 2024
4-6 December (on Zoom)

Book of Abstracts

Digital Resources of the Ancient Near East:
Creation, Application Studies, and Maintenance

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Published November 2024

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Introduction

The digital revolution has fundamentally transformed how we study, preserve, and understand the ancient world. As we navigate this transformation, the growing scholarly community of Digital Ancient Near Eastern Studies (DANES) stands at a crucial intersection between hermeneutic humanities scholarship and data-driven computational methods. The second DANES conference continues to bring together an international cohort of researchers who are pioneering new approaches to ancient world studies through digital and computational technologies.

This year's theme particularly highlights the emergence of sustainable digital infrastructures that enable both innovative analyses and preservation of cultural heritage objects. Several papers focus on the creation and maintenance of comprehensive databases and digital resources, such as our keynote speakers on the Coptic Scriptorium, ARCHIBAB 2.0 for Old Babylonian texts, FactGrid for cuneiform studies at large, and more.

A significant portion of the contributions address the crucial challenge of making legacy data accessible and useful for modern research. This includes projects to digitize and structure historical archaeological records, create standardized formats for 3D annotations, and develop new approaches to spatial data recovery. The attention given to data sustainability, interoperability, and open access reflects the community's commitment to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Through various case studies—such as stylometric analysis of ancient texts, spatial modeling of settlement patterns, and digital documentation of material culture—the papers demonstrate how computational methods can enhance rather than replace established analytical frameworks, while opening new avenues for research and interpretation. The scholars presenting at the conference are not only developing new tools and resources, but are also critically engaging with fundamental questions about how digital methods can best serve

the study of ancient cultures while maintaining rigorous academic standards.

This conference thus presents both a snapshot of current developments in digital ancient Near Eastern studies and a roadmap for future directions. The diversity of approaches and applications suggests that we are only beginning to realize the potential of digital documentation and computational analyses in advancing our understanding of the ancient Near East.

The virtual format of the conference itself reflects the increasingly interconnected and collaborative nature of modern scholarship, enabling participation from researchers across multiple continents and time zones. This accessibility aligns with the broader goals of the DANES network to foster an inclusive community of practitioners and to facilitate the sharing of knowledge and methodologies across disciplinary boundaries and expertise.

Keynote Speakers

Caroline T. Schroeder is Professor of Women's and Gender Studies at the University of Oklahoma, where she also serves as Senior Faculty Fellow at the Data Institute for Societal Challenges. Her research explores how ancient religious communities understood family relationships, gender, and childhood. A pioneering scholar in digital humanities and early Christian studies, Schroeder's research bridges ancient texts and modern technology through innovative digital approaches. As co-director of [Coptic SCRIPTORIUM](#) and the [Coptic Dictionary Online](#) (winner of the 2019 DH Awards for Best Tool), she has transformed the accessibility and digital study of Coptic texts. Her recent book "Children and Family in Late Antique Egyptian Monasticism" (Cambridge University Press, 2021) was a finalist for the American Academy of Religion Book Award. Schroeder's groundbreaking work has earned her numerous other accolades, including the Jane Dempsey Douglass Prize from the American Society of Church History.

Amir Zeldes is Associate Professor of Computational Linguistics at Georgetown University, where he directs the Georgetown University Corpus Linguistics Lab (Corpling@GU). His particular focus is on how computational models can help us better understand complex discourse-level phenomena like coreference and causality, that humans process effortlessly in everyday communication. Currently serving as president of the ACL Special Interest Group on Annotation (SIGANN), Zeldes has made significant contributions to the field through his work on predictive models of referentiality, discourse relations, and entity tracking in conversation. A recipient of multiple NEH grants, his projects include the development of major corpus resources like the Georgetown University Multilayer Corpus (GUM) and the Universal Dependencies treebank for Coptic, as well as co-directing [Coptic SCRIPTORIUM](#), and developing the [Coptic Dictionary Online](#) (winner of the 2019 DH Awards for Best Tool).

DANES 2024 Program

All hours are shown in Central European Time.

Wednesday, December 4: Workshops

- 3:00pm-4:30pm [*Fine-Tuning LLMs for Ancient Language Processing*](#)
Shai Gordin and Emma Yavařan (Digital PastS Lab, Ariel University)
- 5:00pm-6:30pm [*Towards \(Semi-\)automatic Annotation of Cuneiform Signs*](#)
Jan Philipp Bullenkamp (Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg) and Timo Homburg (Mainz University)
- 7:00pm-8:30pm [*Building The FactGrid Cuneiform Project: How to Make a Knowledge Graph for Cuneiform Studies*](#)
Adam Anderson (UC Berkeley)

Thursday, December 5

- 4:00pm-4:10pm Opening Remarks: Hubert Mara (FU Berlin)
- Keynote Session**
Moderator: Eliese-Sophia Lincke, FU Berlin
- 4:10pm-5:00pm *Digital Resources for Coptic - 12 Years of Coptic Scriptorium*
Caroline T. Schroeder (University of Oklahoma) and Amir Zeldes (Georgetown University)
- Long Talks* **Databases and Infrastructure**
Moderator: Marine Béranger, FU Berlin
- 5:15pm-5:45pm [*ARCHIBAB 2.0: A New Website for Archival Documents*](#)

[from the Old Babylonian Period!](#)

Christian Gaubert (CNRS) and Antoine Jacquet
(Collège de France)

5:45pm-6:15pm [Creating Digital Datasets from Legacy Records: The Example of the ELAMortuary Burial Database](#)
Yasmina Wicks (University of Naples "L'Orientale")

6:15pm-6:45pm [Archaeology Information Modeling - Conceptualization and Pilot Study of BIM-Based 4D Excavation Database Systems](#)
Bjarne Kortmann (BerGSAS/FU Berlin)

Short Talks **Computational Archaeology**
Moderator: Hubert Mara, FU Berlin

7:00pm-7:20pm [XRONOS as a Resource for Archaeological Chronology in West Asia](#)
Joe Roe and Martin Hinz (University of Bern)

7:20pm-7:40pm [Publishing and Sharing Photogrammetry Models in Archaeology](#)
Michael Eisenberg (University of Haifa)

7:40pm-8:00pm [The Corpus of Stamp Seals from the Southern Levant](#)
Ben Greet (The University of Zurich)

8:00pm-8:20pm [Spatial Data Recovery and Mapping of Survey Data for the Negev Casemate Sites in the Negev Highlands, Israel, from the 10th century BCE](#)
Jan Jackson (Pennsylvania State University)

Friday, December 6

4:00pm-4:50pm **Poster Session**
Moderator: Avital Romach, Yale University

This session will commence with five minute lightning talks by each of the presenters, followed by separating into breakout rooms where the audience can ask the presenters questions

about their posters and hold discussions.

[DEMCC - The First Online Cuneiform Texts Database in China](#)

Changyu Liu (Zhejiang Normal University), Qier Zhang (Zhejiang Normal University), Jing Tan (Xingzhi College Zhejiang Normal University), Muzhe Han (Jiangsu University), and Émilie Pagé-Perron (University of York)

[Developing an OCR - Wikibase Pipeline for Place Names in the RGTC Series](#)

Matthew Ong (University of Helsinki)

[Modeling Network Connections of the Settlements from the Cuneiform Map CBS 10434](#)

Marina Redina-Thomas (Cornell University)

[Still GLoWing: Developing Synergies in the Assembly and Development of Sustainable Open Access Data in Cuneiform Studies](#)

Rune Rattenborg (Uppsala University)

**Not presenting during the conference*

[The SIANE Device: Advancing Digital Documentation of Ancient Near Eastern Cylinder Seals](#)

Lara Bampfield (Oxford University), David Young (University of Southampton)

[Use of Relational Databases for Medium Sized Corpus Study: Case Studies of Old Babylonian Nippur and Ur \(2016-1841 BCE\)](#)

Andrew Deloucas (Harvard University)

Long Talks

Ancient Language Processing

Moderator: Shai Gordin, Digital Pasts Lab, Ariel University

5:00pm-5:30pm

[Tracing Translation's Footprints: A Stylometric Analysis of Ancient Greek and Coptic Texts](#)

Noam Bar David (Bar Ilan University), So

Miyagawa (The University of Tsukuba), and
Eliese-Sophia Lincke (FU Berlin)

5:30pm-6:00pm [Reassessing the Paradigm of Syriac Hellenization in Late Antiquity: A Computational-Quantitative Analysis of Greek Words in Syriac Literature](#)
Noam Maeir (Hebrew University of Jerusalem)

6:00pm-6:30pm [Constructing a Knowledge Graph Lexicon for Sumerian: Methodology, Collaboration, and Integration into Wikidata's Linked Open Data Framework](#)
Timo Homburg (Mainz University) and Adam Anderson (UC Berkeley)

Short Talks

Linked Data and Networks

Moderator: Adam Anderson, UC Berkeley

6:40pm-7:00pm [SemitiLEX: A Prototype Online Etymological Dictionary and Annotated Text Collection](#)
Na'ama Pat-El, Danny Law, and Todd Krause
(University of Texas, Austin)

7:00pm-7:20pm [Musical Instruments in Ancient Mesopotamia \(MIAM\): A Semantic Media Wiki Database and Lexicon](#)
Dahlia Shehata and Benedetta Bellucci
(University of Würzburg)

7:20pm-7:40pm [Comparing Knowledge Organization Networks](#)
Haleli Harel (Hebrew University of Jerusalem)

7:40pm-8:00pm [The Long History of Using Computational Methods in the Humanities. The Example of Peter Damerow](#)
Christian Schröter (geb. Vater; Akademie der Wissenschaften und der Literatur | Mainz - Digitale Akademie)

8:00pm-8:10pm Closing Remarks (Shai Gordin, Digital Past Lab, Ariel University)

Building The FactGrid Cuneiform Project: How to Make a Knowledge Graph for Cuneiform Studies

Adam Anderson (UC Berkeley)
workshop

FactGrid is a historian's database built on Wikibase technology, which provides an open source Knowledge Graph database for anyone to use for free. While the learning curve for Wikibase can be quite steep, the lasting benefit of this new technology provides a powerful way to build customizable databases which can be edited by many researchers at once all around the world.

Knowledge Graphs (KG) are quickly becoming a rich and deep resource for the ongoing training of Large Language Models, because they embody the very characteristics which these new AI tools lack. On the one hand, because AI is composed of datasets which are taken from social media and other online data, their structure is very broad, unreliable, and non-specific, which has thus far led to hallucinations and overgeneralizations. In contrast, KGs have deep domain-specific data which can be difficult to find online, and they are often curated by specialists and therefore highly accurate. On the other hand, AI models are more convenient in that they can be queried with natural language, and recent improvements are showing signs of thought processing and reasoning. In contrast, KGs can be difficult to query and while the knowledge in these data structures evolve as they are curated over time, they do not yet come with an agent to interpret the data or to provide summary observations. Therefore, if we were to project outcomes for FactGrid beyond the structured accumulation of online resources for cuneiform studies, it would be to amass both broad and deep types of datasets to build a comprehensive model capable of querying and delivering the results of these knowledge-bases using natural language.

The aim of this workshop will be to provide a high-level description of how to build a Knowledge Graph database for working with all available online cuneiform texts. Beginning with an intro to the Wikibase technology, we will first learn how to build your own

Wikibase database using Docker. After a brief overview of the code for working the Wikibase APIs in Jupyter notebooks, we will learn how our notebooks can be replicated for adding the catalog data from the online databases, such as CDLI, and ORACC, with links to the additional resources, such as eBL and BDTNS, etc. Next we will describe how the texts are brought into alignment with the different formatting styles (CDLI-ATF, ORACC-ATF, Unicode, etc.), and how they are published in wiki-page transcripts. Lastly, we will cover how Wikidata lexemes can be used to lemmatize the cuneiform texts, and provide every conceivable form of linguistic annotations (e.g. orthography, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, etc.).

After covering the steps of how to build your own Wikibase clone of the FactGrid Cuneiform project, we can then explore how to integrate the resulting Knowledge Graph into different language models and NLP workflows. As hinted to above, we are working on a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) layer to provide SPARQL queries from natural language prompts, as well as deep learning models for linking multilingual data points in the KG, in order to support the development of word sense disambiguation for the lexemes of a given language, in our case, Sumerian, Akkadian, Ugaritic, Elamite, Hittite, etc.

The SIANE Device: Advancing Digital Documentation of Ancient Near Eastern Cylinder Seals

Lara Bampffield (Oxford University), David Young (University of Southampton)
poster

The Seals and their Impressions in the Ancient Near East (SIANE) device is a tool developed to enhance the visual documentation and analysis of ancient cylinder seals. Born out of a collaborative effort between archaeologists and computer scientists, the SIANE device was designed to overcome the challenges posed by the intricate designs and often worn or damaged surfaces of these artefacts. The development process focused on balancing high-resolution imaging with the practicalities of processing large datasets, resulting in a versatile tool that supports both 2D and 3D imaging methods.

This poster will provide an overview of the technical development of the SIANE device, detailing iterative improvements to both its hardware and software components. The device employs advanced lighting techniques and high-precision scanning technology to capture fine details, making it ideal for recording the complex iconography found on cylinder seals. The SIANE device represents an advancement in the digital documentation of Near Eastern artefacts, offering a powerful tool for creating accessible, high-quality datasets.

We will also demonstrate how the data produced by the SIANE device can be used in conjunction with image annotation software to enhance research possibilities, offering new ways to engage with and analyse these ancient artefacts. This example highlights the broader applications of the datasets produced by the SIANE device, showcasing their potential across various fields of digital scholarship.

Use of Relational Databases for Medium Sized Corpus Study: Case Studies of Old Babylonian Nippur and Ur (2016-1841 BCE)

Andrew Deloucas (Harvard University)
poster

This poster presentation details the methodology of my ongoing Ph.D. dissertation, tentatively titled "The Organizational History of Old Babylonian Nippur and Ur". This study advances civic and social organizational analyses of the cities of Nippur and Ur, previously explored by Elizabeth Stone (1987) and Marc van de Mierop (1992). The objective is to create comparative models of urban organization in southern Babylonia, analogous to those developed for Sippar (Harris 1975) and Assur (Larsen 1976).

To achieve this, I employ a microhistorical approach, utilizing archival research and prosopography. I organize and analyze a corpus of approximately 4,000 entries using relational database management software (Claris's FileMaker). Data is sourced from online databases such as CDLI, ARCHIBAB, and Ur-Online, as well as museum collections hosted by the University of Chicago's Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures, the Penn Museum, and the British Museum.

The methodologies employed include archival research—focused on excavation, museum collections, and published data—and prosopography. Regarding this second method, I seek to replicate and contribute to the work of scholars such as Kraus (1951), Charpin (1986), and Goddeeris (2016), while also establishing new dossiers. This poster will highlight initial findings from my fourth chapter, which examines texts dated from 2016 to 1841 BCE.

Publishing and Sharing Photogrammetry Models in Archaeology

Michael Eisenberg (The Zinman Institute of Archaeology, University of Haifa)

short talk

Photogrammetry is used nowadays as the main graphic documentation tool in archaeology in the field and for artifacts documentation and analysis in the lab. Despite its common use, the still problematic issue is how to share the models, allowing colleagues and non-professionals an easy direct access to view and critique on the material finds. The scholars are left with imperfect and complicated processes, and leading journals in archaeology fail to provide a clear platform for viewing the models. The most widespread solutions present currently in scholarship is to upload the whole of the raw data, so that the reader is forced to go through a lengthy process of downloading the large dataset and opening it with specialized computer programs.

Here, we suggest one solution, based on iTwin Capture Modeler by Bentley software, which includes an optional integrated web viewer for the models to be shared online without any additional software. We have developed and tested a web-based interface with secured protocols for sharing of independent photogrammetric models, used for publications, class teaching, lectures and team-shared analysis tool.

ARCHIBAB 2.0: A New Website for Archival Documents from the Old Babylonian Period!

Christian Gaubert (CNRS) and Antoine Jacquet (Collège de France)
long talk

The database of the Archibab project has been online since 2010 and is widely consulted since then by both assyriologists and people interested to discover the rich archival documentation from the Old Babylonian period. Its content (7 572 fully transliterated, translated and lemmatized Old Babylonian letters or letter extracts, 3 427 legal documents and 7 642 administrative documents, as well as several hundred texts of various or indeterminate types, i.e. a total of 23 963 texts or 67% of the 35 623 Old-Babylonian archival texts currently published) and the research possibilities it offers (constitution of coherent corpora by place, date, archive and/or lemma) make it the most comprehensive database on this documentation today. However the current website is no longer up to the standards expected for such a project and we have therefore undertaken its complete overhaul, aiming at improving the tool, ensuring its sustainability and offering a better experience to a wider audience.

The current Archibab website is run by the 4th Dimension (4D) software as a copy of the core database. A purely JavaScript interface interacts directly with 4D's internal language procedures. This technical base leads to a number of shortcomings, the most salient being the lack of responsiveness and speed. The lack of modularity of the code and the general obsolescence of the website's design are the cause of some crippling defects on the website, such as the absence of pagination, difficulty in scrolling long lists, or the inability to adapt to different screen sizes. It also lacks API access for data and an authentication mechanism for staff access.

In thinking about the changes to make, we came up with a list of features that could really improve the website without disrupting its internal structure, or only marginally at first. The 4D database is to remain in use on a daily basis for data entry and searches, for its very structure remains robust and allows ondemand upgrades. New

requirements included the possibility to combine all our search criteria (metadata and text), to have consistent URLs that can follow and retrieve these search combinations, the possibility to highlight lemmas and syllables searched for in the text, and to offer internal navigation within the corpus through hyperlinks on lemmas, sites, archives, bibliographic references, etc. We also enhanced the transliteration section, by linking it to notes and translations, aligning them precisely whenever possible, and by displaying the associated documentation (handcopies, photographs, videos) side by side with the text without having to leave the website. The historical geography research carried out over many years in conjunction with the Archibab project (HIGEOMES project) has also been given new impetus on the new website. We can now display on a map the archaeological sites whose location is known, and for each site it is possible to click on links to texts found or written on that site.

After a long phase of development and an intensive test period, the Archibab team will very soon be ready to deliver a public version of this new website, which is hosted in Paris by the Collège de France with the support of the CNRS (UMR 7192-PROCLAC). This conference is the ideal opportunity to present not only the contents of the database and the extended research possibilities our website now offers, but also to discuss the technical choices that have been made in the field of information technology, the corrections we now need to make to our data on an ongoing basis, as well as the further developments that are being considered to make the data fully open and interoperable.

Fine-Tuning LLMs for Ancient Language Processing

Shai Gordin and Emma Yavaşan (Digital Past Lab, Ariel University)
workshop

The application of large language models (LLMs) offers promising new methods for processing and analyzing ancient languages with limited resources, such as Hittite. This workshop will focus on utilizing LLMs for Hittite glossing, exploring both the opportunities and challenges that arise when adapting these models for low-resource languages. Through hands-on exploration, participants will gain insights into the key steps involved in fine-tuning LLMs and evaluating their effectiveness for specific linguistic tasks, with a focus on Hittite texts. Broader implications for other ancient languages will also be considered.

Participants will work with fine-tuned LLMs to generate glosses for Hittite texts, focusing on practical applications and model evaluation. Attendees will engage in hands-on activities, exploring how these models handle the unique challenges posed by Hittite's word forms and inflections. The workshop will provide a practical framework for adapting computational tools to the study of ancient languages and offer participants a chance to assess how these methods can be applied to their own research contexts.

Key topics covered will include:

1. Introduction to Large Language Models for Ancient Languages: A brief overview of the role of LLMs in processing ancient, low-resource languages, focusing on their potential for tasks like glossing. Special attention will be given to the unique challenges of applying these models to Hittite texts.
2. Dataset Preparation and Adaptation: An exploration of how datasets are prepared for LLM fine-tuning, with a focus on the specific requirements for Hittite. This will include practical insights into dealing with limited resources and adapting datasets to capture the complex morphology of Hittite.
3. Model Application and Evaluation: Participants will explore

practical applications by working with fine-tuned models to generate glosses for Hittite texts. The focus will be on evaluating the models' performance in handling Hittite's word forms and inflections, and on comparing different strategies for assessing model outputs.

The Corpus of Stamp Seals from the Southern Levant

Ben Greet (The University of Zurich)
short talk

Stamp seals, a common but highly valued object in the ancient Near East, are densely packed with insights into various social, economic, political, and cultural-religious issues, providing a unique and multi-faceted prism through which to study the ancient societies of the region. It was this aspect that drew biblical scholar Othmar Keel to study these objects and his mission to publish all stamp seals from excavated contexts in the region resulted in his multivolume *Corpus der Stempelsiegel-Amulette aus Palästina/Israel* and *Corpus der Siegel-Amulette aus Jordanien* (1995-2017). Whilst these volumes now form standard reference works for the miniature art of the southern Levant, roughly 4,500 seals remained unpublished as of 2017.

To bring Keel's vision to completion and engage with the digital humanities turn, a four-year Swiss National Science Foundation Sinergia grant was awarded to the project Stamp Seals from the Southern Levant (SSSL) - an initiative that culminated in the newly developed Corpus of Stamp Seals from the Southern Levant (CSSL) database (cssl.levantineseals.org). This open-access, collaborative and expandable research tool currently includes all of the data from the stamp seals currently published by Keel, as well as additional entries from sites not included in the previous corpus that will become publicly available alongside printed volumes of the corpus in 2024 and 2025, with the intention of moving to a digital-first model of publication following the completion of the initial corpus. Yet this project wasn't merely a transfer of printed data to a static database, but an endeavour to maximise the potential of this new digital format through innovative approaches to the data and developing an adaptable and accessible user interface that serves a multitude of research questions.

These new approaches include: (1) enhanced detail and data granulation that could facilitate more comprehensive and better structured data collection and input that in turn allowed for more intricate queries.

This, in turn, led to the incorporation of additional and novel information in the field of glyptic studies. (2) The design and implementation of a hierarchical taxonomy for iconographic motifs on stamp seals to also allow for standardisation and ease of queries, but with the use of shared IDs create the basis for open linked data between glyptic databases. (3) Integrating the ability to express doubt or suggest alternatives, which is sometimes forgotten in the design of static data fields, especially related to more complex rubrics with multiple interpretations such a typology, material, colour, and dating. (4) The implementation of an extensive programme of high resolution photography of almost 2,000 objects from 76 sites across the southern Levant, including innovative methods such a backlighting and focus blending that had yet to be applied to glyptic photography. (5) The acquisition and inclusion of new measurements of physical objects - such as weight - and the design and successful employment of an accurate digital measuring tool within the CSSL database. (6) With this detailed and granulated data we can then create complex queries of the material, but added the ability for users to easily graphically represent these queries spatially, temporally, and typologically. (7) Furthermore, our mapping software was designed to allow scholars the ability to define and select their own regions when examining the data - to better allow for the broadest possible interpretations of the data geographically. (8) Many aspects of the data - including other objects, hieroglyphs, and bibliography - are then cross-referenced throughout the database and easily displayed to users through tooltips.

Perhaps the most important lesson we learnt through the development process, though, was that our end goal was to create a database that adapted dynamically to the research needs of both current and future scholars. Thus, rather than solidify a static database, CSSL is designed to be constantly updated and adapted to future needs. Currently there are plans to introduce a hierarchic taxonomy organisation of materials; the introduction of a Mohs Hardness category; and inclusion of petrographic analysis data, to name a few examples.

With these new tools and this inherent ability to dynamically adapt

the CSSL database, we not only seek to provide an equitable and open digital reference tool for any scholar interested in stamp seal data from the southern Levant. But we also believe it has the potential to significantly augment the worth and longevity of prior scholarly accomplishments by providing a research tool that permits users to construct custom queries to answer their unique research questions and, in doing so, it aspires to enhance the efficacy and creativity of present-day and future scholars in their exploration of the cultural-historical narrative of the southern Levant through the lens of ancient miniature art. Furthermore, as the CSSL database is open source, open-access, and operates via FAIR principles, we also believe it can serve as a template for or bridge between established and developing glyptic databases across regions and disciplines.

Comparing Knowledge Organization Networks

Haleli Harel (Hebrew University of Jerusalem)
short talk

The talk “Comparing Networks” showcases how we can access the inherent semantic landscapes of various ancient lexicons, visualize their structures, and then compare datasets to identify recurring patterns across different scripts and pinpoint language-specific tendencies in knowledge organization. In the first part of the talk, the collaborative research tool iClassifier will be presented (© Goldwasser, Harel, Nikolaev, published in Harel et al. 2023, 2024). Studies of the ancient world require specialization. Thus, we often delve deep into the complex world of a single cultural reality. The second part of the talk will be devoted to answering the question of how we can bridge philological disciplines and compare semantic frameworks across languages. Parameters for cross-linguistic annotation will be presented, and challenges in comparative lexicography will be discussed.

I will explore the parameters one can use to compare network structures by experimenting with a comparison of several networks of different ancient Egyptian texts. This question will be examined theoretically, considering what indicators can be compared across various networks’ data (such as adjacency matrices or node centrality). I will then discuss global vs. local patterns characteristic of networks and specify how they manifest in classifier-based networks. I will survey how other research fields have analyzed the comparison of network structure parameters. Finally, I will apply similarity measures to a sample of classifier-based semantic networks and suggest what we can learn by comparing networks.

Towards (Semi-)automatic Annotation of Cuneiform Signs

Jan Philipp Bullenkamp (Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg)
and Timo Homburg (Mainz University)
workshop

We will start with a talk on advances in the assisted annotation of media, e.g. renderings and 3D models containing cuneiform signs.

At first we present an extension of the Gigamesh Software Framework which is able to load 2D-created annotations of rendering images and to export them as 3D annotations as well as create 3D annotations directly on the mesh.

Further we discuss how 3D annotations might be stored in an interoperable exchange format and highlight ongoing discussions of the NFDI4Objects standardization group for 3D annotations. This will help the audience to gain an insight on future interoperability of annotation formats in different 3D processing software.

The second part of our talk will feature a watershed-based approach for cuneiform wedge detection and classification according to the wedge types in PaleoCodage. We evaluate its success rate, its compatibility with and applicability in the workflow of a computer scientist and its benefits to Near Eastern studies.

Afterwards we will demonstrate use cases for both aforementioned technologies. We then want to discuss the applicability and feasibility in an annotation workflow for Near Eastern scholars together with the participants.

Constructing a Knowledge Graph Lexicon for Sumerian: Methodology, Collaboration, and Integration into Wikidata's Linked Open Data Framework

Timo Homburg (Mainz University) and Adam Anderson (UC Berkeley)
long talk

This paper delineates the methodology and execution of a knowledge graph (KG) lexicon for the Sumerian language in Wikidata, which began in 2021. The primary objectives of this chapter are twofold: firstly, to raise greater awareness regarding a collaborative linked open data (LOD) initiative in Wikidata for Sumerian and Akkadian, and secondly, to expound upon the ontology employed for constructing the KG lexicon specific to Sumerian within Wikidata. The overarching objective of our work is to improve the accuracy and accessibility of linguistic analysis for Sumerian, facilitating a more comprehensive understanding and leveraging modern computational linguistic tools. To address these goals, this chapter provides a detailed and systematic guide for the types of triple statements (i.e. properties and items, as edges and nodes), most useful for linguistic annotation in Wikidata lexicography. The outlined workflow not only enhances the accessibility of Sumerian language resources but also contributes to the broader landscape of ancient languages and linguistic research.

As a tribute to the openness of the project, the ontology of the lexicon in Wikidata has been customized for the Sumerian language thanks to the collaborative work of Timo Homburg, a computer scientist in Mainz, Germany, and Adam Anderson, a research partner with UC Berkeley, California. The linguistic data in Wikidata can be accessed in the tool PaleOrdia (<https://situx.github.io/paleordia/language/?q=Q36790&qLabel=Sumerian>), a fork from a preexisting lexeme visualization tool Ordia (<https://ordia.toolforge.org>), which has been customized for cuneiform languages and mitigates the need to query Wikidata manually using the SPARQL query language.

The workflow commences with the utilization of Oracc's Sumerian

glossary, as disseminated in the Electronic Pennsylvania Sumerian Dictionary 2 (<https://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/epsd2/>). Then significant steps are taken to structure the resultant data into RDF triples within Wikidata Lexicography, with each lexeme intricately linked to the corresponding cuneiform signs in published sign lists. The project entails substantial engagement in graphemic and morphological analysis, and the preparations involved in linked data for seamless integration into Wikidata. This undertaking serves as a testament to a holistic approach in digitizing and linking ancient linguistic data, aligning it with contemporary technological applications in lexicography while upholding the standards within Assyriology. The project stands as a pivotal bridge between ancient linguistics and modern digital technologies, offering tools and methodologies that could significantly enhance research in historical linguistics. By facilitating a deeper understanding and broader dissemination of Sumerian language resources, it promises to enrich scientific inquiry and educational outreach in the fields of Assyriology and computational linguistics.

Spatial Data Recovery and Mapping of Survey Data for the Negev Casemate Sites in the Negev Highlands, Israel, from the 10th century BCE

Jan Jackson (Pennsylvania State University)
short talk

During the 20th century archaeology made enormous strides in the development of methods to document finds, which included recording information about geographic locations and arrangement. However, much of this data was collected half a century or more ago, and is often in a state where its spatial information is very imprecise. The techniques of recording used processes or systems which had significant limitations on location precision or accuracy given the tools of the era. This means that today we may lack verification that objects or features are where they are purported to be.

In recent years, the science and technology of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has made it possible to expand the utility of spatial data for scholarly use. As a result, there are immense opportunities to mine spatial information from older archaeological sites and surveys. Revisiting and enhancing data collected in the 20th century can allow it to be integrated with current excavations and surveys, studies and research. This paper discusses one approach to developing such a geospatially-enhanced database which incorporates information about feature attributes and surrounding infrastructure. Some of the problems encountered are also covered.

As a case study, I will use the 10th century casemate sites in the western Negev Desert in Israel, often referred to as Negev Fortresses, to explore the various issues involved in processing previously collected archaeological data to make it useful for cartographic mapping and analysis. These archaeological sites were surveyed and excavated between the 1960s to the 1990s. The original publications were put out in print as 'mapbooks' and subsequently have been made available online by the Israel Antiquities Authority's Survey of Israel. I begin with an overview of the original publications and data

storage. The processing workflow includes a discussion of the original method used for recording location data and the subsequent need for data correction, the design and development of spreadsheets for data organization, conversion of data into spreadsheets and then into shapefiles or geopackages, and the use of GIS software for mapping and data analysis. I also discuss ground-truthing, assessing the accuracy of the original data recording, and verification or correction of the site locations using modern satellite imagery. The resulting dataset, still a work in progress, will be made freely available for download.

The Negev dataset was initially recorded in a mapping system which subsequently was discontinued, so adjustments had to be made to the original coordinate locations for all items. A large part of the data was published only in Hebrew, and translation was also necessary. After this was accomplished, I was able to create shapefiles for use in GIS software based on the modified records. However, a check soon revealed that features were usually not in their expected location, which led to the use of satellite imagery to locate and update the actual placement of features. This further involves the selection of imagery with a high enough spatial resolution to be able to identify an individual element.

There is a huge amount of recorded data from older excavations that is currently unusable in a GIS. My experience with the dataset under discussion offers a number of lessons in how to go about processing such data to make it accessible and usable for academic research. I also discuss some of the problems encountered which suggest future directions for research and technology to improve our ability to ingest, evaluate, and ground-truth historical archaeological data using contemporary methods.

Archaeology Information Modeling - Conceptualization and Pilot Study of BIM-Based 4D Excavation Database Systems

Bjarne Kortmann (BerGSAS/Freie Universität Berlin)

long talk

Excavation documentation is a constantly evolving field, experiencing more rapid and diverse developments than excavation methodology itself. The critical importance of proper documentation and reliable research data management in our discipline is increasingly recognized, with the FAIR principles for research data—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—now familiar to nearly all archaeologists. While there is broad consensus on these principles and great similarity in the data categories produced (such as texts, coordinates, 2D representations, etc.), significant heterogeneity exists in the database systems used. Moreover, few databases can integrate all excavation data categories, resulting, for example, in the isolation and underutilization of 3D data despite its high potential.

In the construction industry, the commercial benefits of interoperability and reusability—universally acknowledged as fundamental for research data management—led to the development and widespread adoption of Building Information Modeling (BIM). BIM aims to fundamentally improve data management, which, in both construction and archaeology, has traditionally been characterized by isolated 2D drawings, separate data forms, and countless individual files. By integrating all project data with three-dimensional representations into a single digital model, BIM creates a 3D model that functions not only as a visualization tool but also as an object-oriented database. As with CAD and GIS, the most widespread BIM software are commercial products employing their own data structures and proprietary data formats. To make BIM data interoperable, an open data standard was developed by a large consortium that simultaneously provides an ontology of objects, relationships, and other data definitions, as well as a flexible, future-proof file format. This standard is

referred to as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC). In recent years, the first software capable of natively creating BIM data in that format—rather than just converting to it on export—has been developed, strictly adhering to the data structures mandated by IFC. Although still in an early testing phase, this software, BlenderBIM, provides a promising Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) solution for the creation of IFC BIM data.

While BIM has been applied in archaeology for the management of historic buildings and virtual architectural reconstructions, its potential for the comprehensive documentation of excavations has not been previously explored.

This talk addresses the potential advantages of using a BIM-based data management approach for excavation data compared to traditional methods and examines the extent to which existing BIM data standards and software can be utilized for this purpose. The presentation draws on research conducted as part of a master's thesis, which led to the conceptualization of a methodology based on open data standards, ontologies, and open-source software, and the creation of a holistic 4D database system. This preliminary concept, termed Archaeology Information Modeling (AIM), represents a novel approach to excavation data management and was tested on a conceptual, semantic, and technological level in an initial case study using data from an excavation area of the DFG long-term project in Yeha, Ethiopia.

Tracing Translation's Footprints: A Stylometric Analysis of Ancient Greek and Coptic Texts

Noam Bar David (Bar Ilan University), So Miyagawa (The University of Tsukuba), and Eliese-Sophia Lincke (Freie Universität Berlin)
long talk

Style-measurement (or stylometry) is a common tool among historians and philologists, offering applications for corpus clustering, authorship attribution, lexico-statistical analysis, and more. In this lecture, we will present two case studies showcasing the usage of stylometry as a tool for translated language detection.

The first case demonstrates translation detection in Coptic. Coptic, the final stage of the ancient Egyptian language and liturgical language of the Coptic Orthodox Church, emerged from Demotic around the 2nd century CE and served as one of Egypt's primary languages from the 3rd century alongside Koine Greek. Following the Arab conquest in the 7th century, Coptic gradually gave way to Arabic, ceasing to be a native spoken language by the 17th century. It retains many grammatical and lexical elements of earlier Egyptian chronolects while incorporating a significant Greek loanword vocabulary. The language played a crucial role in early Egyptian Christianity, preserving important religious texts. These works form the core of the corpus presented in our paper. In order to build a digital corpus for clustering with the Stylo package in R, we utilized digital editions from platforms such as Coptic Scriptorium and the Coptic Old Testament Virtual Manuscript Room. Additionally, we employed OCR to digitize texts not yet available electronically. In analyzing this corpus—comprising both translations from (Koine) Greek and original compositions in (Sahidic) Coptic—we demonstrate that the source language is one among several features influencing clustering behavior. Additionally, we explore how the sizable Greek loanword corpus impacts the clustering patterns of both translated and original Coptic texts.

The second case study presents translation detection in Ancient Greek, offering a multi-layered analysis of both late and archaic Greek

works, as well as translations into Greek from Semitic languages. In order to measure the vectors between different Greek texts, the data was taken from open-source databases for Ancient Greek (such as the Perseus Digital Library) and cleaned of digits and English letters. The preprocessed text files were analyzed by means of the Stylo package. This analysis revealed significant differences both between Archaic Greek and Classical/Koine Greek texts, and between those original Greek texts and works translated from Semitic languages. Additionally, some lexical-statistical phenomena were discovered by means of Voyant Tools and using scripts for frequent-words ratio measurements, contributing to a better understanding of the machine clustering process. In addition to the Stylo output and the statistical analyses, a heat map was generated, highlighting anomalies in the frequency distributions of specific words across authors. This visualization provided an additional layer of insight into the stylometric patterns observed.

These two case studies illustrate the potential of stylometry as a valuable tool in the field of computational humanities: By leveraging computational tools, we contribute to long-standing philological debates, offering new insights that complement traditional approaches such as close-reading, linguistic analysis, and historical research. Furthermore, this study emphasizes a key methodological consideration in this field: the importance of scholarly expertise in creating comparative corpora, which profoundly impacts the statistical results. The traditional scholarly skill of familiarity with literary sources remains essential for building balanced and relevant corpora.

DEMCC - The First Online Cuneiform Texts Database in China

Changyu Liu (Zhejiang Normal University), Qier Zhang (Zhejiang Normal University), Jing Tan (Xingzhi College Zhejiang Normal University), Muzhe Han (Jiangsu University), and Émilie Pagé-Perron (University of York)
poster

DEMCC, the abbreviation of Database of Early Mesopotamian Cuneiform Contracts, is not only the first online database of Early Mesopotamian cuneiform contracts in China, but also the first online cuneiform texts database in China so far, which is the sub-project of the Key Project on Philosophy and Social Sciences of Ministry of Education of China (Grant No. 23JZD040). DEMCC aims to establish an integrated and comprehensive digital humanities platform that integrates data collection, text mining, multi-label classification, multimodal data association display, multi-source data fusion, and visualization capabilities for the future. Its users or beneficiaries cover Assyriologists and scholars in law history and related disciplines. Accompanied by transliterations and translations in both English and Chinese, the cuneiform texts, primarily in Sumerian with some Akkadian, are exclusively contracts as well as court records (di-til-la) dating among three periods, Old Sumerian (Uruk, Fara, Pre-sargonic or Early Dynasty), Old Akkadian (Sargonic) and Neo-Sumerian (Ur III). In early Mesopotamia, there are mainly two types of contracts, sale and loan contract, as well as court records (di-til-la) exclusively in Ur III period, which objects involve real estate (land, house, orchard, etc.) and chattel (slave/person, barley, silver, etc.), as well as labor force. This database not only provides with transliterations and bilingual translations (English and Chinese), but also contains many specific and specialized fields, such as contracts' type, formule, terminology, object and amount, both parties (seller/buyer in sale, lender/borrower in loan), witness, oath, other related information, and general information like one text's publication, period, provenience, collection, and corresponding CDLI number. The database system architecture currently under development leverages FileMaker Pro, a reputable database management

system renowned for its technical stability. This platform facilitates data fusion and association with other relational databases, including MySQL and Oracle, thereby laying a solid foundation for subsequent semantic association representation, knowledge integration with third-party datasets like CDLI, and ensuring semantic interoperability. This poster intends to comprehensively introduce the overarching objectives, technical architecture, data flow model, and diverse functional modules of the DEMCC database. Additionally, it will provide a concise overview of the various technical solutions proposed for full-stack development, ensuring a holistic understanding of the platform's capabilities and potential. The users can find every information and data through searching different fields. DEMCC plans to be online and usable in 2026 for free, with a hyperlink to CDLI.

Reassessing the Paradigm of Syriac Hellenization in Late Antiquity: A Computational-Quantitative Analysis of Greek Words in Syriac Literature

Noam Maeir (Hebrew University of Jerusalem)
long talk

This study re-evaluates the paradigm of Syriac Hellenization by analyzing the integration of Greek words in Syriac literature through the use of computational-quantitative methods. By leveraging linked data of the lexicographical database Sedra and the Syriac literary database Simtho, the study enabled to analyze an extensive list of Greek foreign words in a massive corpus of Syriac literature according to the hitherto impossible distinction based on frequency. The results reveal new insights regarding the distribution and diachronic influx of Greek loanwords in Syriac literature from the 4th to the 13th centuries CE.

Traditionally, Syriac-Greek cultural interactions during late antiquity were characterized by scholars as exhibiting a gradual process of cultural and linguistic assimilation of Greek elements, i.e., a gradual Syriac Hellenization (e.g., Brock 2017). A mostly pre-digital quantitative analysis of Greek loanwords served as a powerful foundation for the Hellenization paradigm. Accordingly, an increase in the influx of Greek loanwords over the course of late antiquity provided empirical evidence supporting a pattern of Syriac Hellenization. Yet, recent advances in the digitization of Syriac texts and resources now enable a renewed quantitative analysis of the phenomenon.

Firstly, Sedra, a new lexicographical database of the Syriac language has come online (<http://sedra.bethmardutho.org>). By digitizing almost all of the Syriac lexicographical works into the database, Sedra now includes more than 34,700 lexemes, each representing a specific Syriac word, with tagged information regarding its trilateral root, grammatical category, related glosses, derived Syriac words, and, if relevant, the etymology of the word. Thanks to the systematic tagging

of Syriac etymologies built into Sedra, and its open-access policies, it is now possible, for the first time, to compile a comprehensive list of Greek loanwords that are found in Syriac literature. Another significant development in the digitization of Syriac culture is the creation of Simtho (<https://simtho.bethmardutho.org>). Simtho contains over 12,000,000 words, from over 500 texts, written by 143 authors. For each word, Simtho provides detailed information regarding all excerpts in which a word appears, including date, author, title, etc. And so, linking data from Sedra and Simtho enabled to create a corpus of all the dated mentions of Greek words found in an extensive corpus of Syriac literature, so that each word can be described on the basis of its frequency and on a diachronic axis.

The results of the analysis enabled to distinguish, quite clearly, between many infrequent words vs. a few highly frequent words, regardless of their diachronic behavior. In other words, the distribution of Greek foreign words in Syriac literature is non-Gaussian. This suggests that a more nuanced classification of Greek foreign words in Syriac might be merited. Indeed, when taking the diachronic behavior into account, highly frequent Greek words entered into Syriac only during a limited and early period within late antiquity, witnessed primarily by the 4th century, and to a much lesser degree during the 5th and 6th centuries. As opposed to this, the influx of infrequent Greek words by Syriac writers appears to be a local literary phenomenon witnessed throughout the entire history of Syriac literature, until the 13th century and beyond.

In other words, the patterns and periodizations emerging from the quantitative analysis seem to question the usefulness of the paradigm of Syriac Hellenization in its ability to explain or describe the results of this study. Rather than a single pattern of cultural interaction, I argue that the results point to two different kinds of Syriac-Greek interactions, one related to the linguistic process of Greek loanword integration, occurring within an early and limited time period, and another relating to local cultural processes of infrequent usages of Greek foreign words, seen over a millennium.

Developing an OCR - Wikibase Pipeline for Place Names in the RGTC Series

Matthew Ong (University of Helsinki)
poster

I present the development of a semi-automated workflow that extracts and digitally stores certain 'geographically relevant information' related to place names inventoried in the publication series *Répertoire géographique des textes cunéiformes*. Geographically relevant information goes beyond the place names themselves and includes schematizing the spatial relations and other geographical information discussed in the prose section of each entry.

This schematized information is then imported in a Wikibase hosting a linguistically annotated corpus of Akkadian, adding an additional layer of cross-linked information. This workflow involves:

1. Training and fine-tuning of an OCR model tailored to the format of the RGTC print publications.
2. Applying text-processing scripts that correct some of the OCR results themselves, generate additional training data, and improve the results of the extraction script.
3. Structuring the extracted results so they can be stored as geoJSON objects.
4. Importing those objects into the Wikibase.

In particular, I focus on volume seven of that series, which deals with certain first millennium place names. The benefits of this work include a reasonably accurate digital copy of the place name entries within an RGTC volume, an OCR model which can be applied to similarly-structured volumes, and an example of how the spatial information within that volume can be represented as linked open data within Wikibase.

SemitiLEX: A Prototype Online Etymological Dictionary and Annotated Text Collection

Na'ama Pat-El, Danny Law, and Todd Krause (University of Texas,
Austin)
short talk

Creating vocabulary lists for the purpose of linguistic comparison and genealogical classification has a long history in historical linguistics in general, and Semitic linguistics in particular. However, existing resources for Semitic languages have certain limitations that we seek to address through the development of SemitiLEX, an accessible database with rich supporting annotations, glosses, and commentary. Existing etymological dictionaries of Semitic languages primarily focus on the root and often provide only partial information about other features. But Semitic lexica contain more than just a root. Semitic nouns may carry information about gender, gender markedness, nominal pattern, plural selection, and nominal class. Many of these features are lexically determined and, therefore, unpredictable, yet existing databases traditionally do not include such key information.

To address this lacuna, we are developing SemitiLEX. This resource will allow linguists, Semitic scholars and language learners to easily access quality information about grammar and vocabulary, across the Semitic family, as well as contextualized readings of key primary texts in Semitic languages. SemitiLEX incorporates traditional lexical information (semantics, etymology) in a comparative lexical database, but expands each entry to include additional grammatical information: e.g. morphological patterns, gender, number morphology, verbal stem, thematic vowel, and types of verbal complements associated with each headword. The system handles complex scripts; combines right-to-left writing alternating with left-to-right; and provides linguistic, cultural, and historical annotation appropriate for Semitists, linguists, and general audiences.

SemitiLEX will also encompass an annotated text collection. Texts will illustrate important features of each of the languages included. Each

text will provide a word-by-word analysis, providing meaning, grammatical form, and commentary. The resource will thus serve not only as a database for individual words and meanings, but also for grammar more broadly and for contextualized readings of key texts from early Semitic languages.

We plan SemitiLEX to be an open access resource that aims to serve both specialists and non-specialists alike. The system will allow a variety of modes of access to users from a range of backgrounds. This will include the ability to switch between original or romanized scripts, as well as modes of search directly via headwords or more broadly via classes of meaning. Researchers will also be able to export the entire database into a variety of formats for further analysis. We envision SemitiLEX as a point of intersection for a range of disciplines, as well as a point of departure for future cumulative, collaborative efforts.

Still GLoWing: Developing Synergies in the Assembly and Development of Sustainable Open Access Data in Cuneiform Studies

Rune Rattenborg (Uppsala University)
poster

From 2020 to 2023, Geomapping Landscapes of Writing (GLOW), a research project hosted by Uppsala University Department of Linguistics and Philology, fielded an innovative research programme for large-scale data assembly and research on the materiality of writing in the cuneiform world. This poster presents an overview of this programme, exemplifying the potential of data integration and best practice approaches for how small and medium research projects may engage with and contribute to open research data repositories, building synergies and furthering the sustainability of research data in a digital, open access environment.

Through a broad survey of the full cuneiform corpus, covering 400,000 inscribed artifacts, encountered everywhere from Rome to Kabul, and spanning a period of some three millennia of early human history, GLOW has delivered several standalone indices for reuse in research and teaching, and built a tailored dataset along the lines of the Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI) data model. This has allowed direct publishing of project data to an established online research platform seeing 20-30,000 visits per month on average. Furthermore, GLOW has helped updating and expanding the CDLI data model, including especially archaeological and collection data for the entire corpus and support of the building of a publications data crowdsourcing feature now supporting a bibliography of 20,000 references linked to the CDLI artifacts catalogue and metadata tables.

In negotiating the many institutional and financial challenges facing small and medium-scale research projects in the humanities today, an understanding and willingness to engage with and reuse knowledge nested within open research communities can work wonders. GLOW offers a number of important lessons on how high impact can be achieved at

low cost, and how sustaining research data for the future can be helped by augmenting and strengthening existing platforms for open research, ultimately to the benefit of all parties involved.

Modeling Network Connections of the Settlements from the Cuneiform Map CBS 10434

Marina Redina-Thomas (Cornell University)
poster

This poster presents my work in progress, which is a part of my doctoral research on the rural settlements of the Nippur province during the Middle Babylonian period (1595-1155 BCE). It focuses on modeling network connections between settlements depicted on the Kassite cuneiform map CBS 10434 and other settlements co-attested with them in the archival administrative documents. The modeling is conducted with the help of Gephi software, which allows to visualize settlement network connections, trace their frequency, and identify network clusters that could be representing agricultural or taxation units.

Cuneiform map CBS 10434 from the collection of Penn Museum is one of the few examples of visual representations of the ancient settlements, fields, and canals that are mentioned in the documents from the Kassite Nippur and Dūr-Enlillē archives. Many of these documents are records of taxation, storage, and disbursement of agricultural produce, predominantly barley. Only three of the settlements depicted on the map, Tukultī-Ekur, Kār-Nuska, and Dimtu, which located in the area enclosed by canals and a borderline, are co-attested, i.e., appear together in the same documents, while none of the other geographical features shown on the map, except for the canal Tukultī-Ekur, are co-attested with them. At the same time, Tukultī-Ekur, Kār-Nuska, and Dimtu are often found in tabular compound accounts with other recurring settlements that are not depicted on CBS 10434, e.g., their annual revenues in barley and other crops are accounted together with those of several additional places. I consider these co-attestations to be meaningful and showing the connections between the settlements at least from the point of view of the administrative system that produced these documents. They display certain patterns that provide insights into the economic and geographical connectivity of the settlements and the way ancient bureaucrats saw the provincial agricultural landscape from the

administrative perspective.

The social network model, where nodes stand for settlements and edges for connections between them represented by their co-attestations, is a productive research tool that makes evident particular clusters of a larger administrative and agricultural area stretching beyond the limits of the territory depicted on the map CBS 10434. It adds a degree of certainty to the disjointed attestations of the settlements, which were provincial agricultural producers, in the textual corpuses and brings relative historical geography of the Kassite Nippur region one step closer to the absolute one.

XRONOS as a Resource for Archaeological Chronology in West Asia

Joe Roe and Martin Hinz (University of Bern)
short talk

XRONOS is an open data infrastructure for the backbone of the archaeological record - chronology. It provides open access to published radiocarbon dates and other chronometric data from any period, anywhere in the world. In this talk, we introduce XRONOS and with an eye on its coverage of West Asia. This currently comprises 22,739 records of radiocarbon dates ranging from 50,000 BP to the present. This makes it one of the better-represented regions of the world in terms of radiocarbon data - largely thanks to a long history of regional compilation. Geographic coverage is relatively even, considering the large differences in historic population density between different parts of the region. A detailed assessment and literature review of the radiocarbon corpus from Eastern Iran shows that XRONOS' dataset is fairly comprehensive, but that the quality of the metadata accompanying individual dates can be substantially improved with the benefit of regional expertise. On the other hand, XRONOS' coverage of other types of chronological information in West Asia is currently limited to rough typological determinations collected alongside radiocarbon data. This produces a marked temporal bias towards the period c. 3000 to 11500 cal BP and limits its usefulness for chronological work in the protohistoric and historic periods of West Asia. Incorporating more types of chronometric data to address this problem is one of our main goals for the development of XRONOS in the near term.

The Long History of Using Computational Methods in the Humanities. The Example of Peter Damerow.

Christian Schröter (geb. Vater; Akademie der Wissenschaften und der
Literatur | Mainz - Digitale Akademie)
short talk

That the Humanities should go digital is a rallying call of the day. This digitality should be data driven, allow collaborative works through networked access, use methods of visualisation - including 3D - and a mixed set of tools out of the artificial intelligence bag. For 'small subjects' - a collection of academic disciplines with little resources and a long tradition - this should be an even higher priority, so the story goes, to further their survival. But is this story based on correct premises? In my short talk I will argue that this is not the case. On the opposite: the small subjects have been - on one hand - centres of innovation for a long time (besides being centres of traditional learning). Digitality is not a new phenomenon, and digital methods have been used here all along, too - following the impact of the 'information age' and 'computational thinking' since it's advent (see e.g. Daubichler/Maieinschein/Renn 2013). This can be shown by the example of Peter Damerow in his various collaborations, who, as a mathematician by training, used computational and statistical code breaking techniques or imaging procedures out of the life sciences to understand Babylonian mathematics. On the other hand there always was theorizing about using tools for academic thought - and this subject did include the reflection about own methods and tools (e.g. Damerow/Lefèvre 1981). Taking a deeper look at Damerows work can just be a first step here - there are more and equally interesting cases of innovative technology use and development of digital methods well ahead of their day, so getting some interesting hints to forgotten lore during discussion is one of the reasons to give this talk. The other reason is to show the usefulness to draw a line between innovative use of new and experimental technology and overreaching technology hype, guided by the theoretical work about 'doing science' that can be found accompanying these early breakthroughs in humanities computing, especially in the 'small subjects'.

Literature:

Damerow, Peter/Englund, Robert K./Nissen, Hans J. (1988), „Die Entstehung der Schrift“, in: Spektrum der Wissenschaft Februar 1988, S. 74-85.

Damerow, Peter/Englund, Robert K./Nissen, Hans J. (1988), „Die ersten Zahldarstellungen und die Entwicklung des Zahlbegriffs“, in: Spektrum der Wissenschaft März 1988, S. 46-55.

Damerow, Peter u. Lefevre, Wolfgang (Hgg.) (1981), Rechenstein, Experiment, Sprache. Historische Fallstudien zur Entstehung der exakten Wissenschaften, Stuttgart: Klett-Cotta.

Damerow, Peter/Meinzer, Hans-Peter (1995), „Computertomographische Untersuchung ungeöffneter archaischer Tonkugeln aus Uruk, W 20987,9, W 20987,11 und W 20987,12“, in: Baghdader Mitteilungen BaM 26, 8-33 u. vier Tafeln.

Damerow, Peter u. Lefèvre, Wolfgang (1994), Wissenssysteme im geschichtlichen Wandel. Berlin: Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte. (=Preprints 5)

Kantel, Jörg/Damerow, Peter/ Köhler, Sarah/Tsouparopoulou, Christina (2010), „3D-Scans von Keilschrifttafeln - ein Werkstattbericht“, in: Wolfgang Assmann, Christiane Hausmann-Jamin u. Frank Malisius (Hgg.), 26. DV-Treffen der Max-Planck-Institute, 22. - 24. September 2009 in Berlin, Göttingen: Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung, S. 41-62.

Laubichler, Manfred D./Maienschein, Jane/Renn, Jürgen (2013), „Computational Perspectives in the History of Science: To the Memory of Peter Damerow“, in: Isis, 104 (1), 119-130.

Musical Instruments in Ancient Mesopotamia (MIAM): A Semantic Media Wiki Database and Lexicon

Dahlia Shehata and Benedetta Bellucci (University of Würzburg)
short talk

MIAM has started April 2024 as a 4-years DFG-funded project with the aim to explore and investigate the musical instruments of Ancient Mesopotamia and Syria. The project is hosted at the University of Würzburg in close collaboration between the department of Ancient Near Eastern Studies and the Zentrum für Philologie und Digitalität "Kallimachos" (ZPD). It further collaborates with external researchers in Jerusalem, London and Paris.

The project's primary work objective is to provide a comprehensive collection of records on or with reference to musical instruments from all periods of ancient Mesopotamia with no restriction to object types. The MIAM-database thus faces the challenge to include metadata sets for all types of records, be they cuneiform manuscripts, images as there are reliefs and figures, or original musical instruments. To meet this challenge, the MIAM-database was created based on Semantic Media Wiki (SMW)-technology with each individual record being represented through an own Wiki-page. SMW has been under active development since its initial release in 2005 with more than 1600 active Wikis today. It is ideally suited for the implementation of semantic database projects and offers numerous ready-to-use components to be easily adjusted to the special needs of the project. Besides the basic object data, the metadata sets were further adjusted to the needs of music-related information, such as building and construction information, materials, and organology, but also playing occasions, musicians, music ensemble size, terminology, and other relevant contextual references. Each record-page further provides visual data, new photographs of object details, and in cases needed also RTI-photography as well as 3D-scans.

But MIAM is more: All information extrapolated and correlated from the records' analysis and interpretation enters the creation of an online lexicon. This includes individual entries for both ancient Akkadian

and Sumerian instrument names and terminology, as well as modern instrument names, under which the analysis of the primarily iconographic data is brought together.

After a short introduction, our presentation will present selected examples of data acquisition and page generation to illustrate the potentialities of the implementation of SMW-technology to analyze records of different genres and types that are nevertheless united by a common theme. To stimulate a subsequent discussion, we will further address existing challenges, for example in text input, editing, and lemmatizing or in introducing visual data.

Creating Digital Datasets from Legacy Records: The Example of the ELAMortuary Burial Database

Yasmina Wicks (University of Naples "L'Orientale")

long talk

Burials were the most ubiquitous site features documented during 20th century excavations at the city of Susa in southwest Iran, having been uncovered in their thousands across all major mounds of the site. Capitalizing on their large number and the long uninterrupted settlement sequence they span, my recent Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship project "Villages to Empire: 4000 Years of Death and Society in Elam (4500-525 BCE)" (ELAMortuary, 2022-2024) at the University of Naples "L'Orientale" aimed to utilize these burials to query social change over the *longue durée*. In this presentation I will introduce the open access ELAMortuary database housing this new digital dataset and discuss the various sources of the burial data. I will focus especially on the digitized open access archives of records generated by Roland de Mecquenem, director of the French archaeological mission at Susa from 1912 to 1939, which provided a significant portion of the burials for the dataset. I will highlight the challenges these records present, some of the strategies used in the attempt to extract and systematize usable data from them, and how it may be possible to now use this large digital dataset. While the database will remain a work in progress for years to come as new data is continually added, I hope that it might stimulate interest in the continued development of methods that can transcend the deficiencies of the legacy records of excavations at Susa, particularly through the application of digital technologies. Indeed, this will be key to the preservation and valorization of Susa's cultural heritage, as it is already for other sites across the Near East. In line with the theme of the conference, I also intend to highlight that my research was only possible thanks to the availability of my sources digitally and openly.